

DETERMINING THE BEST ANNUAL RAINFALL INTERPOLATION FOR BILA WALANAE WATERSHED

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Abstract

Bila Walanae watershed is the largest watershed in South Sulawesi. Water resources management need to take sedimentation analysis into account. However, using USLE as sedimentation analysis requires annual precipitation data in a spatial form. On the other hand, there are many methods of spatial interpolation. The purpose of this study was to determine the best spatial interpolation method for annual rainfall Bila Walanae watershed. Monthly rainfall data from 41 observation points (14 inside watershed, 27 around outside) were used. This study compares four methods of spatial interpolations, such as Inverse Distance Weight (IDW), Thin Plate Spline (TPS), Ordinary Kriging (OK), and modified Regression Kriging (MRK). Additional data for MRK derived from TRMM rainfall estimates (2013-2014) and GPM (2015-2017). Interpolation parameters such as pixel size and variogram models determined in advance while number of neighbour (NN) is 14. Two IDW power (1 and 2) and five TPS regularization setting (1E-5, 1E-4, 1E-3, 1E-2 and 1E-1) is used. Error is generated through the leave-one-out cross validation by calculating RMSE and MAE. Result shows that TPSE-1 generate small error with highest correlation (MAE=648; RMSE=799; r=0.45) followed by IDW (646;799;0.40), OK (666;810;0.43), and then MRK (1410;3176;-0.11). Disuse of outside points increases MAE about 9%. Result of TPSE-1 interpolation is then averaged over five years and compared with land cover. Relatively high annual rainfall pattern is seen in area with forest in southern part of the watershed and around Lake Tempe that has no forest. Projections RCP by 8.5 shows increasing precipitation pattern in those area. Therefore, further studies related to priority of those two regions are needed.

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1. Introduction

Bila Walanae watershed (in Indonesian, *daerah aliran sungai*, DAS) along with 38 other watersheds is under Walanae Cenranae River Basin Region (*wilayah sungai*, WS). The River Region itself is managed by Balai Besar Wilayah Sungai (BBWS) Pompengan Jeneberang. Bila Walanae watershed is the largest watershed in South Sulawesi with an area of approximately 7,770 km² [1]. In the watershed, there is a Walanae River with a length of 250 km [2] and Lake Tempe with an area of approximately 478 km² whose potential of fisheries and agricultures for the surrounding communities [3]. Based on the South Sulawesi Regional Regulation Number 10/2015 [4], Bila Walanae watershed is under restored status, which means the watershed's environmental conditions are not functioning properly. Some consequences of restored status are necessity of comprehensive analyses involving relevant agencies in planning.

In water resources management, one thing that is needed to be considered is sedimentation. Sedimentation has some impacts on declining the ability of rivers and lakes to accommodate the water volume. Low level of river sedimentation is one indicator of successful watershed management [5]. On the other hand, sedimentation study needs good erosion information. Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) method is an erosion model that is often used in erosion studies. One of USLE material is spatial annual rainfall [6]. However, due to limited observations, spatial interpolation needs to be done to get the data. Spatial interpolation method has many variations. For example, in the study of Adhikary et al [7], several interpolation methods were compared to get the best interpolation method for two watersheds. The purpose of this study was to determine the best spatial interpolation method for Bila Walanae watershed's annual rainfall. A simple analysis using result of the best interpolation method results will be done then.

2. Data and Methods

The scope of this study took astronomical border 119.50° E – 120,50° E and 3.25° S – 5.50° S.

Figure 1. Area of study and its elevation (shown by the colors)

The data used in this study were taken from 41 rainfall observation points consisting of 14 observation points in watershed area (in Figure 1, shown by circle) and 27 points outside watershed area (shown by cross). The data used is annual rainfall from 2013 to 2017. Rainfall data used in this study is produced from daily observations. According to the BMKG Chairman's Regulation Number 4/2016, rainfall was recorded at seven o'clock local time which is representing rain events since 24 hours before. So the rainfall data is actually representing rainfall from the previous date [8].

Interpolation methods that are compared in this study are Inverse Distance Weight (IDW), Thin Plate Spline (TPS), Ordinary Kriging (OK), and Modified Regression Kriging (MRK). Equations of IDW are formulated below [9].

$$\tilde{z}_{IDW}(s_0) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i(s_0) \cdot z(s_i) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\lambda_i(s_0) = \frac{\frac{1}{(d[s_0, s_i])^\beta}}{\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{(d[s_0, s_i])^\beta}}; \beta > 1 \quad (2.2)$$

$\tilde{z}_{IDW}(s_0)$ is a interpolation target value at point s_0 using IDW, $\lambda_i(s_0)$ is defined as weighting coefficient for predictors $z(s_i)$ for interpolating at s_0 , and β itself is power parameter. $d(s_0, s_i)$ is euclidean distance between the two points. For OK, the equation is as shown below.

$$\tilde{z}_{OK}(s_0) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i(s_0) \cdot z(s_i) = \lambda_0^T \cdot z(s_i) \quad (2.3)$$

$\tilde{z}_{OK}(s_0)$ is an interpolation's target at point s_0 and then $w_i(s_0)$ are weighting coefficients from solution of these matrices.

$$\lambda_0 = C^{-1} \cdot c_0 \quad (2.4)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} w_1(s_0) \\ \vdots \\ w_n(s_0) \\ \varphi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C(s_1, s_1) & \dots & C(s_1, s_n) & \mathbf{1} \\ \vdots & & \vdots & \vdots \\ C(s_n, s_1) & \dots & C(s_n, s_n) & \mathbf{1} \\ \mathbf{1} & \dots & \mathbf{1} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} C(s_0, s_1) \\ \vdots \\ C(s_0, s_n) \\ \mathbf{1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\lambda_0 = \begin{bmatrix} w_1(s_0) \\ \vdots \\ w_n(s_0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

λ_0 is a weighting matrix consist of weighting for every point and Lagrange multiplier on the last column.

Regression-kriging is an mechanism that first of all, regression is used to estimated rainfall value then the residual of the regression is taken back to the result after being interpolated using kriging. The original equation is as shown below.

$$\tilde{z}_{RK}(s_0) = \hat{\beta}_0 + \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_k \cdot X_k(s) + \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \cdot \varepsilon(s_i) \quad (2.7)$$

The modification is done because in the original equation, correction mechanism using addition so it can make the result become a negative value. The rainfall can not be minus. To avoid the negative result, regression residual is transformed to be a correction factor [10]. After a correction factor has been interpolated using kriging (OK in this case), the result is combined back with multiplication mechanism as shown below.

$$\tilde{z}_{MRK}(s_0) = [\hat{\beta}_0 + \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_k \cdot X_k(s)] * \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \cdot f_{ki} \quad (2.8)$$

f_{ki} itself is defined as coefficients that replace residuals mechanism from unmodified RK.

Thin plate spline is one of spline method using in spatial interpolation. Spline itself is a type of piecewise polynomial function which is preferable to a simple polynomial interpolation

because more parameters can be defined including. For TPS method, detail equations that construct this interpolation method can be read in Donato and Belongie's study [11]. Other variables used for MRK are data Digital Elevation Model (DEM) from Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) also satellite-based rainfall estimation from Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) and Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM). TRMM data is used for year 2013-2014 and GPM data for 2015-2017. SRTM data is downloaded from dwtkns.com/srtm, more detail description of data is available in Jarvis's document [12]. TRMM data used has version 3B42v7 and taken from iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu. On the other hand, GPM data is taken from Huffman's link [13]. More detail about algorithm and resources for TRMM/GPM is explained by at least two other Huffman's documents [14-15]. Regression pattern analysis is carried out first before choosing regression type that can be used properly. Using simple scatter plot, analyses are taken between rainfall and the other two variables. Software used for all four interpolations is System for Automatic Geoscience analyses (SAGA) and for extracting data, R Statistics with raster package is used. SAGA and R Statistics itself are free open sources softwares [16-17]. This study also modifies the scripts from Kurniawan and Makmur's research [18]. Comparing interpolation results from different software is not done in this study.

To determine the best interpolation method, at least there are three ways to find out these are leave-one-out cross validation (LOOCV), n-fold cross validation, and fitting with some hydrological model's output [9, 19]. LOOCV is used in this study because of the observation points is only 14. LOOCV takes one sample point temporarily and then doing interpolation using the rest points. After error is taken at the point, the point is then returned. Same mechanism is done for all fourteen points so every point become a validation point at least once. Validation parameters used in this study are RMSE and MAE [20]. Correlation is also used in this study.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{MSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x - y)^2} \quad (2.9)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x - y| \quad (2.10)$$

Optimum pixel size (PS) for interpolation is determined by equation below using number of observation (N) and area coverage (A) as material recommended by Hengl [21].

$$PS = 0.25 \times 0.5 \times \sqrt{\frac{A}{N}} \quad (2.11)$$

The variogram model used in kriging is justified after variogram plotting is done. The power of IDW used in this study are 2.0 (default from SAGA software) and 1.0. Regularization parameters of TPS used are $1E-5$ (10^{-5}), $1E-4$ (default), $1E-3$, $1E-2$, and $1E-1$ (0.1). Because there are 14 points in watershed region, number of neighbour (NN) is also set to be 14.

3.Result and Discussion

The coverage area of Bila Walanae watershed is 0.600729 degrees square. Equation 2.11 gives 0.0259 degrees as recommendation for pixel size. Minimum distance between points in the watershed is 0.027934 degrees. From this result, PS then is justified using 0.02 degrees.

Figure 2. Variogram of 2015 and 2017

The variogram model of annual rainfall over five years shows similarities with spherical model. Therefore, nugget value = 0 and sill = 1 is then justified to be used so that interpolation results above material points do not change. Due to its similarity, this study uses only single range value that is 1.8 where almost all variograms show relatively flat pattern at that distance. Both OK and MRK use same variogram model and assumption that LOOCV mechanism will not make any variogram model change. Therefore, the variogram model in SAGA is defined as " $1 * \text{ifelse}(x > 1.8, 1, 1.5 * x / 1.8 - 0.5 * x^3 / 1.8^3)$ ".

Figure 3. Scatter plot regression analyses: rainfall-GPM/TRMM (left) and residual-DEM (right)

Scatter plot of regression between GPM and TRMM with observation rainfall shows that the relationship between these two rainfall estimation has significant difference. By using a simple ratio-based correction, it is found that observation rainfall value (Obs) can be approximated through equation $\text{Obs} = 1.061 * \text{TRMM}$ and $\text{Obs} = 5.025 * \text{GPM}$. TRMM estimation is much higher than GPM. Residuals of regression between rainfall and GPM/TRMM are then estimated using DEM. Simple linear equation shows no good regression so polynomial up to power six is done,

$f(\text{DEM}) = 7.3365\text{E-}13 * x^6 - 2.1366\text{E-}9 * x^5 + 2.2287\text{E-}6 * x^4 - 9.8847\text{E-}4 * x^3 + 1.7545\text{E-}1 * x^2 - 1.3010\text{E+}1 * x + 2.6536\text{E+}2$. Overall, rainfall is then formulated into one formula so that the regression used is as follows.

$$\text{Obs} = [f_{\text{ratio_GPM/TRMM}}(\text{SAT}) + f_{\text{polynom6}}(\text{DEM})] * cf_{\text{interpolation}} \quad (3.1)$$

The correction factor (cf) that will be interpolated is defined as rainfall observation divided by the regression result minus one. This is done so that the correction factor that is far from the interpolation material will have value 1. For reversing back to correction factor, the result of interpolation is added by 1 before it is multiplied by regression result.

Figure 4. MAE (left), RMSE (left), and correlation (right)

The graphs above show that MAE and RMSE value of TPS, OK, and IDW are relatively similar. However, correlation between interpolation results and observation points of TPSE-1 is the highest among others (MAE=648; RMSE=799, $r=0.45$). The result also shows that MRK is inferior compared to the others. Although having the most complex mechanism, MRK interpolation generates biggest error (1410;3176;-0.11). It confirms that a bad regression approach brings a high bias or error into interpolation. On the other hand, declining error pattern of TPS can be observed linear with increasing on regularization parameters (from 10^{-5} to 10^{-1}). On the contrary, decreasing of power in IDW reduced the error. IDW shows smaller error but lower correlation (646;799;0.40) but better than OK (666;810;0.43).

Figure 4. 5-years rainfall average, land cover, and projections

Five years results from TPSE-1 interpolation of rainfall are then averaged. The results showed that high rainfall (over 3000 mm per year) occurred in eastern region of Bila Walanae watershed and around Tempe Lake. Relatively low rainfall appears in the downstream region. Compared to land cover map from Ministry of Forestry [22] which are classified as forest, active (residential, agriculture and plantation), and water zone. It can be shown that the eastern region should be prioritized due to its upstream condition and relatively high rainfall. On the other hand, five-year rainfall projection (2018-2022 divided by 2013-2017) from BMKG's (Indonesian Meteorology Climatology and Geophysics Agency) CSIROMK3.6 RegCM4 climate change model indicates that rainfall condition in the future will be similar with today's if adaptation and mitigation of climate change is done (RCP 4.5), while if there is no effort of it or business as usual (RCP 8.5) wetter conditions will occur. Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) themselves are set of projection for climate change study [23]. Worst case shows wet conditions will occur around Tempe Lake area where the surrounding area has transformed to be active area. This shows that climate change can have impact on the region.

Analysis of error (represented by TPSE-1's MAE) in spatial perspective shows some relation with DEM and 5-years rainfall average. It can be said that interpolation's error will be small in area with elevation around 200 m and will rise in coastal areas and in higher area. From the rainfall average, error will increase in areas with relatively higher rainfall. Further studies on the impact of eliminating 27 points around the watershed to TPSE-1 interpolation (with NN = 13) is also done. Moreover, decreasing correlation (from 0.45 to 0.29) and increasing error (MAE from 648 to 270, RMSE from 799 to 916) appears. Error increase about 11 to 14 percent if points around watershed are taken away.

Figure 5. Relation between DEM (left) and rainfall average (right) with interpolation error

4. Conclusion

Based on the result, we conclude that the best method among the four methods is Thin Plate Spline with Regularization 10^{-1} (TPSE-1), followed by IDW, OK, and the worst is MRK. Important notes that should be considered are this study's fixed parameters such as pixel size=0.02, NN=14, 5 TPS' regularizations, 2 IDW's power, variograms used in krigings are sphericals (nugget=0; sill=1; range=1.8), and cross validation method used is leave-one-out cross validation. Thus, different result may occur if the parameters, data, or period used are different. There are some recommendations that can be given based on this study. Further studies on regional priority of the watershed management are needed so that existing resources can be used effectively and efficiently. Shared understanding about maintenance of rainfall observations' quality, quantity, and continuity is needed because it is proved that losing rainfall data around watershed can increase interpolation error. Awareness of climate change should be increased because RCP 8.5 scenario implies that rainfall in area around Lake Tempe will increase. Nevertheless, a complicated interpolation method does not always give a better result.

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